

supplementary irrigation needed, its effect on yield, and the risks associated with rainfed aus and aman rice cultivation on the farm of the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, in 1980-81. The three treatments were 1) rainfed, 2) rainfed with supplementary irrigation to keep the plots saturated, and 3) rainfed with supplementary irrigation to keep the plots under 25-50 mm standing water. The water balance method was used to determine the crop water requirement, with provisions for measuring rainfall, evaporation, and seepage and percolation.

Treatment 3 had yields 8-71% higher than in treatment 1 during aus and 71% higher during aman. Rainfall was 842 mm during aus and 783 mm during aman. Supplementary irrigation was required because of erratic distribution. For treatment 3, 69 mm supplementary irrigation was required in aus and 573 mm in aman. For treatment 2, a 57% higher yield over treatment 1 during aman required only 15 mm supplementary irrigation. Crop water requirements at field level

Supplementary irrigation required (SIR) during aus and aman seasons at rainfall probabilities of 25, 50, and 75%. BIRRI, Bangladesh. 1980-81.

were calculated as 643 mm for aus and 893 mm for aman.

Probability analysis projected that aus rice would require supplementary irrigation in 1 out of 4 yr and aman rice 3 out of 4 yr. The amount of

supplementary irrigation required would vary 0-69 mm with rainfall probabilities of 50-75% for aus and 67-309 mm with rainfall probabilities of 25-75% for aman (see figure). □

Irrigation management for lowland rice under water constraint

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A trial on irrigation practices used IR50 rice on clay loam soil at TNAU during 1985 kharif and 1986 summer. Kharif treatments were 1) continuous 5-cm submergence, 2) saturation to 5-cm submergence, 3) field capacity to 5-cm submergence, 4) a turn system of two 7-cm irrigations at 3- and 4-d intervals in 1 wk, with no irrigation the alternate week, and 5) continuous 5-cm submergence to 30 d after transplanting (DT) and thereafter no irrigation for 4 d, followed by 1 wk continuous submergence. In summer, field capacity submergence was

Water management effects on yield in Tamil Nadu, 1985-86.^a

Treatment	Kharif			Summer		
	Water consumed (mm)	Yield (t/ha)	WUE (kg/ha mm)	Water consumed (mm)	Yield (t/ha)	WUE (kg/ha mm)
1	1639	5.30	3.2	1651	5.18	3.1
2	971	5.19	5.8	1013	5.04	5.0
3	723	4.18	6.4	1430	5.48	3.8
4	917	4.58	6.0	960	4.83	5.0
5	1463	4.98	4.1	1387	5.24	3.8
CD at 5%	—	0.57	—	—	0.46	—

^aWUE = water use efficiency.

replaced by a partial turn system — 4 d no irrigation followed by 1 wk continuous 5-cm submergence up to 30 DT — and then continuous submergence.

Saturation to 5-cm submergence

saved about 40% of the water needed for continuous submergence without significantly affecting yield (see table). Under the turn system, yields were 14% less in kharif and 7% less in summer. □